

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF APPLYING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES TO THE TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article focuses on modern technologies in teaching and highlights how they can be used effectively and its creative methods to apply.*

Keywords: *technology, interactive method, creativity, pedagogical technologies.*

The role of geography is incomparable in forming a sense of respect for universal and national values in the young generation, in building a sense of national pride in them. This places a great responsibility on teachers. In order to fulfill them, the modern teacher must be armed with advanced experience and scientific achievements.

Studies have shown that only knowledge acquired through thinking and observation is well preserved in memory. New pedagogical technologies that have passed the test of time in many developed countries of the world are significant in that they are highly effective in realizing the purpose of the lesson, as all attention is focused on increasing the student's activity.

Currently, a number of developed countries have accumulated a lot of experience in the use of pedagogical technologies that increase the educational and creative thinking of students and guarantee the effectiveness of education, and the methods that form the basis of this experience are called interactive methods. The interactive method of education has been widely used in pedagogical literature since the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century and is used in the field of education. Its main goal is only one, to make students interested in learning independently, to work more on themselves, to read additional literature, to education and upbringing in line with the times, to bring up a perfect person who can think independently serves.

Interactive methods are such methods that students interact and the method that implements the interactive learning process - the word "interactive" is taken from the English language, "Interact", i.e. Inter is "mutual", "act" is "movement, means "mystery, activity".

The lesson in interactive methods encourages the student to think creatively, actively solve the received information, express his opinion freely, take initiative, find solutions to problems in groups, work in cooperation, and express his opinion in writing.

The organization of the lesson on the basis of interactivity takes place in such a way that not a single student is left out in this process, that is, they have the opportunity to openly express what they see, know, and think.

During educational processes based on conversation, the student learns to think critically, to find a solution to complex issues based on analysis, to search for information accordingly, to express some alternative opinions freely in mutual discussions, and such skills are formed. In the organization of interactive lessons, it is possible to use individual, pair work, group work, research-based projects, role-playing games, working with documents, working with information sources, and creative work in the educational process. Currently, various forms of interactive methods have been proposed by methodologists and practicing teachers.

It is possible to obtain the expected results if using the above with a certain goal in mind, creating a problem, preparing students to work in this process, and using it in situations with certain skills. It's best to have a well-thought-out, comprehensive focus on the problem at hand.

In order to conduct work in any of the above-mentioned forms, to organize a lesson, it is necessary to create the concept of each activity, on the basis of this, its sequence, regulation, work procedure, goals, and expected results should be determined in advance and the students should be informed about it.

In interactive teaching, a learning environment is organized, a comfortable environment is created, a well-organized learning environment:

Assists in studies and research;

He will have materials for conducting various studies;

Stimulates creativity;

Develops social and communicative skills;

Enables the exchange of ideas and information;

Stimulates speech development;

Forms the skills of independent acquisition of information;

Develops lifelong learning skills;

Includes resources for obtaining information in various ways;

They will have the opportunity to work with reference books, dictionaries, encyclopedias, geographic maps, a computer, various tools and materials for conducting experiments.

It is possible to demonstrate the development of the following characteristics in students during the course of the lesson using interactive methods.

Students are taught to master through independent analysis, to think creatively, to think freely based on personal conclusions. The skills of being able to think against foreign thoughts and to defend one's consent are formed.

Without giving ready-made knowledge to the student, his knowledge acquisition skills are formed by searching, finding, and processing knowledge from textbooks, the Internet, and various other sources. An opportunity is created for creative observation through the acquired knowledge. The student is taught to work with textbooks, read, study, write a synopsis, acquire independent learning skills using additional literature.

It is guaranteed that all students in the group will learn at the level of their abilities. In this case, the student's ability to use the acquired knowledge in life and practical activities is determined by his skills and qualifications.

All students can achieve the same results if all teachers-students can learn to work on the basis of interactive methods and apply it to their educational activities.

Advantages of organizing the lesson using interactive methods: teaching content leads to better learning; in time, educational relations are established between students, teachers, and students, teaching methods take different forms during the educational process. (individual, pair, group, large groups), the educational process is highly motivated by satisfying the educational need, the educational material is well remembered by mutual information giving, receiving, and processing, the student the skills of entering into mutual communication, expressing opinions, exchanging opinions are formed, during the learning process - the student's self-evaluation, critical view develops, the lesson becomes an interesting subject for the student, a creative approach to the learning process, a positive attitude is manifested, it leads to the ability of each student to think

independently, to work, to observe, in interactive lessons, the student only learns the educational content not only learns, but also develops his critical and logical thinking.

In such conditions, the teacher must have highly developed thinking skills, problem-solving skills, and the ability to solve problems in a timely manner.

The higher the level of interactivity, the more effective the educational process will be.

The influence of educational methods on the results of remembering information

In this, the technique of graphic organizers, ways and means of data analysis, comparison and comparison, ways and means of problem identification, analysis and planning of its solution are important methods.

When the learning process is organized on an interactive basis:

1. The student's mutual activity increases, the skills of cooperation and creativity are formed.

2. Skills for working with the curriculum, program, textbook, standard criteria, manuals, subject content are formed.

3. Independent reading, working, mastering of educational content and text becomes daily personal work.

4. The student gets used to expressing his opinion freely, defending his opinion, being able to prove and confirm it.

5. Most importantly, didactic motives are created during the educational process. That is, the student's needs, wishes, and desires are satisfied. The student's interest increases in the learning process. This situation raises the student to a higher level in achieving educational goals.

The main essence of interactive teaching is that during the teaching process, all students become participants in the learning process, they understand the discussed problems, the development of events and incidents, identify problematic situations, look for ways to solve them, and recommend the most optimal option.

Interactive methods have the following features:

Communication training, which is an important vital human need, is used at all stages of the process.

In the process of education, students are given equal opportunities to show their strength, knowledge, and talent.

It allows students to work cooperatively in small groups.

Students understand each other, listen, work together and makes it possible to solve problems together.

What are the advantages of organizing the lesson in interactive methods

Teaching content leads to better learning.

In time, educational relations are established between students, teachers and students.

Teaching methods take different forms in the educational process. (individual, couple, group, large groups).

The educational process becomes highly motivated by satisfying the educational need.

Educational material is better remembered by mutual information giving, receiving, and processing.

The student develops the skills of communicating, expressing opinions, and exchanging ideas.

During the learning process, the student's self-evaluation and critical view develop.

For the student, the lesson turns into an interesting content of the taught subject, a creative approach to the learning process, a positive attitude is manifested.

Each student will be able to think, work, and observe independently.

In interactive lessons, the student not only learns the educational content, but also develops his critical and logical thinking.

Of course, the organization of interactive lessons has its own disadvantages.

1. The educational process requires spending a lot of time.
2. It will not be possible to properly control all students during interactive training.
3. When studying very complex materials, students cannot fully and clearly solve the problem, in such conditions, the role of the teacher is low.
4. Due to the participation of weak students who are studying in groups, there are cases where even strong students get low marks or grades.

The conclusion is that in such conditions, the teacher should have a highly developed thinking ability, observation of problems, and the ability to solve problems in a timely manner.

When organizing a lesson in interactive methods, it is necessary to start with the development of the student's personality by creating a foundation for himself. That is, the reader:

to gain knowledge based on independent reading and reading;

to self-realization, to gain self-awareness;

to look confidently at one's strength and capabilities;

to look at educational work with a sense of responsibility;

to be able to independently organize one's activities, to enjoy every minute;

to be able to arouse desire for educational work;

to be able to show activity in any situation;

in particular, it is necessary to learn to make effective use of current information sources as the main goal.

Therefore, the creation of technology of self-development of the student is one of the urgent problems that await its solution in front of the science of pedagogy and didactics.

Nowadays, when it comes to applying new methods to the educational process, the use of interactive methods is understood. In the educational processes based on interactive methods, the student learns to think critically, to find a solution to complex issues based on analysis, to search for information, to express some alternative opinions freely in mutual discussions, and such skills are formed.

The main essence of the use of interactive methods is that during the educational process all students become participants in the learning process, they understand the discussed problems, the development of events and phenomena, identify problematic situations, search for ways to solve them, and recommend the most optimal option.

When using interactive methods, students are able to think critically, analyze information sources, solve complex problem situations, draw conclusions based on the analysis of the opinions of other participants in the group, participate in discussions, communicate with other people, students acquire the skills to understand each other, work in cooperation and harmony.

Interactive methods used in educational practice include "Charkhpalak", "FSMU", "Insert", "Elpigich", "Bummering", "Zakovatli Zukko", "Decision tree", "Black box", "Contrary relation", "Bliss game" and many other types. However, significant work has not been done in the field of using them in geography education. However, there is a great opportunity to use these methods in geography classes, in particular, in teaching world economic and social geography. The procedure for organizing and conducting practical training using these methods is different, and the effective

and successful use of these methods in the educational process depends on the pedagogical skills and breadth of thinking of the geography teacher.

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